

A Study on Quality of Digital Teaching at times of COVID' 19 Pandemic

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Abstract: Educational organizations are the mirrors of the society. Quality education is the prerequisite for development of just society and quality citizens. Educational organizations are involved in vital task of providing education, which is an ongoing process. One of the most important tools in effective educational practices, in effective teaching is consistency. Therefore, may what be the circumstances, it is imperial for any educational organization to ensure consistent learning for their students. Educational institutions happen to be the centres of human resource development and the learners who come out of these centres are expected to go to the society and take up some responsibility including business. Good human resource with ethical and moral values will develop good business and good business will ultimately give good service to the society. It is imperative for any educational organization to ensure consistency and quality in its educational practices. In the times of extreme situations such as outbreak of pandemic due to COVID'19 which was being witnessed world across; challenged the academicians across the globe to evolve with novel way of educating the learners and sustain the consistency of teaching learning process.

With motive of ensuring consistency in pedagogic practices, world over the digital educational practices were employed at time of extreme COVID'19 virus outbreak. A study on quality of digital education was done in one of the private university ; based on academic practices in the university at times of COVID'19. The data on the academic practices was collected from the students using research tools such as digital questionnaire was analyzed digitally – to arrive at the findings; which are presented in this paper.

Keywords: Digital, Education, learner, pedagogy.

1. INTRODUCTION

“Teaching is the highest form of understanding’ – Aristotle

‘Teaching might even be the greatest of the arts since the medium is the human mind and spirit.’ – John Steinbeck

Educational organizations are the mirrors of the society. Quality education is the prerequisite for development of just society and quality citizens. Educational organizations are involved in vital task of providing education, which is an ongoing process. One of the most important tools in effective educational practices, involving effective teaching is consistency. Therefore, may what be the circumstances, it is imperial for any educational organization to ensure consistent learning for their students. Educational institutions happen to be the centres of human resource development and the learners who come out of these centres are expected to go to the society and take up some responsible roles. Intellectually advanced and skilled human resource with ethical and moral values will develop high quality professionals and such individuals will ultimately provide good services to the society. It is imperative for any educational organization to ensure consistency and quality in its educational practices. In the times of extreme situations such as outbreak of pandemic due to COVID'19 which was being witnessed world across; challenged the academicians across the globe to evolve with novel way of educating the learners and sustain the consistency of teaching learning process.

Concept of Digital Learning: Digital learning is also called as electronic learning – E learning. Technology enabled learning is called as **Digital learning**. It can also be defined as the instructional practice that strengthens student’s learning experience using technology. Modern day computers and electronics all use binary language comprising of binary digits (1s and 0s) to construct data. Information and instructions created with these digits are therefore called digital information. The Learning that uses this digital information is called digital learning. Consequently, digital learning means learning using electronic devices. In all the present times computers and electronic gadgets binary digits 0s and 1s is used to construct data. The instruction made using digits is called digital instruction and the learning happening there by is called digital learning. Thus the learning facilitated by electronic devices is called as Digital Learning

Need and Importance of Digital Learning:

The traditional teaching strategies facilitate effective learning – wherein the learner and the teacher are physically in same environment. It is called as Face to Face learning. It is more preferred way of learning – however it creates barrier in learning when the teacher and the taught are geographically separated. It limits the reach of learning. If the teacher has to reach a mass at a given time , has to reach learners stationed at different corners of Globe, the use of technology is required to be made to ensure the teacher reaches learners stationed at geographically different locations at the same time in effective way. The present day learner is of digital era – the digital learning therefore become imperial at students get easily acquainted with it facilitates active participation – more engaging sessions can be designed through this forum through actively learning engaging methods such as Gamification, role playing ,team work, reverse teaching, peer education, problem-solving and storytelling.

Importance of Digital Learning:

Digital Learning is the most effective method of teaching for the situations where the teacher and the taught that are geographically at far distance. It provides interactive and memorable experiences than voluminous textbooks or one-sided lectures, they provide better context, a greater sense of perspective, and more engaging activities. It is most promising method of educating learners in large number at same given time. It is called as the latest, modern pedagogic practices which enables availability of the learning resources around the clock and all around the year. It shifts the honours of learning from the teacher to the students. The role of the teacher in Digital education is of facilitator – provider. It is up to the students to make the best of the virtual deliberations; this implies that digital learning makes the learner more responsible, more attentive, and more aware unlike the traditional teaching strategy where the responsibility of effective learning for students is on teacher. Digital education stimulates among the learner self-learning strategy, sharpens student’s critical thinking skills and analytical skills. Over and above this it promotes teamwork, group learning, accountability and cooperative learning skills.

The advantages of digital learning – digital literacy generated among the learners through the digital education can be summarized with help of below given picture:

Figure 1: Advantages of Digital Literacy

Source:<https://www.google.com/search?q=digital+literacy&tbm=isch&ved=2ahUKEwi>

Modes of Digital Education:

There are diverse modes of providing digital education and creating digital literacy. Online classes, virtual meetings, webinars, virtual conferencing, Gamification and much more can be conducted by variety of platforms as through Google Meet, Microsoft teams, WebEx, Zoom and many more which makes the students smart learner – away from rote learning and passive learning – it stimulates among the learners rational thinking , ability to select what they want, what benefits them. Generates higher order thinking skills such as application, analysing, synthesizing and creating. Social skills such as team building, sharing, collaborating, cooperating and contributing. It performs immensely in personality building and confidence building of the learner

Figure 2: Digital Platforms

Figure 3: Modes of Digital Teaching

2. METHODOLOGY

A survey Research was conducted to study the quality of Digital teaching at times of COVID'19 outbreak in the 7 colleges of a private university.

The main objectives of the study were to

- Study the quality of online teaching conducted in the university during the times of pandemic
- Derive the extent of effective virtual engagement of the students during the time of pandemic by the university

Research Questions:

1. How are the online classes conducted in the colleges under the study at times of Pandemic?
2. Was the Prescribed time table followed while delivering content digitally?
3. Were the online classes interactive and interesting?
4. Were the students receiving assignments, notes and study material related to the concepts taught?

For understanding these research questions, following methodology was used by the researcher.

Population: All the students of the 32 colleges of the Private University with average 1000 students in each college were considered as population for the study

Sample for the study: A random sample of 873 students from the 2020 -2021 batch was taken for the study.

The sample taken was a- representative sample formed by taking 10% student from total strength of students from each college considered for the study.

Data collection: The data was collected by administering a close ended digital questionnaire – a Google Form on the sample.

Data interpretation and analysis:

The data collected by digital questionnaire was analysed digitally and is presented graphically as follows:

Online classes are conducted as per the Time table Shared

Among the 873 students 90 % of the students strongly agreed that the online classes were conducted as per the time table shared, 5% students disagreed while 2% of students agreed with the statement.

The Extent of Online classes being conducted In interesting and interactive way

873 responses

38.8% students are of the opinion that most of the time the online classes were conducted in interesting and interactive way, 31.8% students shared that the classes were always conducted in interactive and interesting way while the rest were of the opinion that the classes were monotonous and one way.

Frequency of internet problem faced during the classes

873 responses

In order to facilitate good quality online class which were conducted by the professors stationed in the Parul University Campus – high frequency bandwidth internet facility was provided to all the stakeholders within the campus.

To check the consequences of the same, when the students were asked regarding the efficiency of online classes – related to internet – technical problems faced during the online class, most of them were of the view that the internet problems were minimum, few of them shared that it did occur of some occasions, while some of them found it always.

The reflections of the students are governed by the internet facility used at their end and also by their liking towards particular subject.

Video lectures, Notes And Quiz are being shared in Google Class Room

873 responses

To ensure that students get reference for self study on the topics taught, there is a regular practice of sharing content in the Google Classroom – a Google tool for interacting virtually with learners. To this most of the students reflected that the content is shared with students regularly which helps in effective learning.

3. FINDINGS

The major findings of the study were that the quality of digital learning, virtual teaching in the university was of good quality, it was liked by the students.

The digital mode of teaching was introduced for the first time in the university to meet the circumstances developed, yet was implemented effectively is reflected in the feedback from students that

- The online classes were held as per shared time table,
- The classes were interactive and interesting
- There were minimum technical issues faced
- Post classes reference was provided regularly

All this performed in ensuring good quality of digital teaching

The strategy adopted by the University of integrating digital mode in providing education to the students in extreme times of COVID'19 outbreak proved to be very useful. It helped in ensuring consistency in academic practices.

The efforts from all the stakeholders - the management in facilitating digital education by providing needful infrastructure, teaching staff by adapting the new way of delivering content and students by responding positively contributed in ensuring the sustenance of essence of academic practices.

4. CONCLUSION

India's Destiny is being shaped in Four Walls" (Education Commission 1966). In the present 'Yantra Yug – Digital era' the walls have extended. The class rooms have become virtual, the interactions and instructions are provided virtually – digitally but the essence of learning is sustained as required to generate quality citizens – effective work force. The organizations that modify them self as per the societal needs and as per the circumstances sustain and flourish. They keep contributing to the society. The study presented here is a sound example of the same.

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